

Occurrence and Distribution of Microplastics in the Northern Bay of Bengal: A Case Study on the Coast of Sonadia Island

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ABSTRACT

Microplastic (MP) pollution has become a significant global environmental issue due to its persistence and ecological risks across terrestrial and marine ecosystems. While MPs have been extensively documented in beaches, rivers, and deep-sea sediments, research on island ecosystems, particularly in the Northern Bay of Bengal, remains limited. This study examines the occurrence, distribution, and ecological risk of MPs in Sonadia Island's beach sand, addressing a critical knowledge gap. Beach sand samples were collected from five high-tideline stations on Sonadia Island, with MPs isolated via density separation, filtration, and stereomicroscopic analysis. The mean concentration of possible microplastics (PMPs) was 17.68 ± 7.88 particles/kg, lower than many global beaches but still significant. Fibres were dominant (74%), followed by fragments (18%), films (7%), and foams (1%), with 52% of MPs sized 0.3–1 mm. Transparent particles were most abundant (72%), though colored MPs (red, blue, green, black, and white) were present. Elevated fibre proportions suggest origins from fishing gear and industrial discharge. Contamination Factor (CF) and Pollution Load Index (PLI) values >1 confirmed moderate to considerable pollution. This study provides baseline MP data, revealing moderate contamination dominated by fibres, necessitating improved waste management in fisheries and industries. Recommended mitigation measures include stricter regulations, community clean-ups, and sustained monitoring to reduce ecological risks.

1. Introduction

Microplastics (<5 mm) are well-documented marine contaminants that originated from the direct release of plastic particles as a

consequence of the fragmentation of larger plastic items (Frias et al., 2016; Thompson, 2015). Microplastic pollution is equally

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received:

25-09-2025

Accepted:

02-12-2025

KEYWORDS

Microplastics;
Possible
Microplastic; Marine
Pollution; Island
Ecosystems; Risk
Assessment;
Contamination
Factor

widespread on land and in freshwater as in the marine environment (Rochman, 2018). Since the commercial plastic production began around 1950, society has become increasingly dependent on it. Their affordability, mobility, adaptability, and dependability have boosted global demand (Tajwar et al., 2022). Since 1950, global plastic output has increased at an annual rate of 8.4%, reaching around 380 million tons per year (Symeonides et al., 2021). The increasing production contributes significantly to microplastic discharge, with an estimated 12 billion metric tons of plastic waste projected to accumulate in landfills or spill into natural habitats by 2050, representing a more than 250% increase from 2015 levels (Geyer et al., 2017). According to this projection, *NUTEC Plastics | IAEA (n.d.)* noted that the ocean will contain one tonne of plastic for every three tonnes of fish by 2025, and by 2050, there may be more plastic than present. Similarly, EcoWatch (2016) reported that emissions of microplastics range from 0.5 to 1.4 million tonnes per year, with a midpoint estimate of 0.95 million tonnes. Additionally, this report also revealed that about 80% of waste deposited in the ocean comes from land.

Xiang et al. (2022) categorise microplastic particles into two main types- primary and secondary microplastic- based on their origin. Primary microplastics are manufactured for specific applications, such as in drug vectors, personal care products, cleaning agents, and pharmaceuticals (Boakye et al., 2025; Gouin, 2015). Microbeads, resin pellets, and discharge from washing machines to the wastewater contain primary microplastics (Xiang et al., 2022). Secondary microplastics originate from the degradation of bigger plastic products caused by environmental variables such as UV radiation, physical

abrasion, and temperature variations (Shahul Hamid et al., 2018). These plastics may potentially be smaller than 5 mm due to fragmentation. Microplastic particles larger than 1 mm can be visually inspected using a microscope. Secondary microplastics have a definite shape, brightness, colour, and hardness (Zobkov & Esiukova, 2018). Plastics weather due to wave activity, retention time, and photochemical reactions, and break down into smaller pieces. As the particles get smaller, different organisms of the food chain take them as food and confirm the presence of MP in their gastrointestinal tract (Hale et al., 2020). These particles are recorded as films, foams, fibres, fragments, and irregular shapes (Wright et al., 2013).

Microplastics contain different polymers, including polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), polystyrene (PS), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), polyurethane (PU), polyamide (PA), and polycarbonate (PC). These polymers are recorded in the marine environment as well as freshwater ecosystems (Bar et al., 2025; Xu & Gao, 2025). Each polymer has its own chemical traits that shape the durability, degradability, and environmental interactions (Horton et al., 2017). For example, PET is a common material for fabrics and packaging. PE and PP are often found in plastic bags, bottles, and containers. PVC is well-known for its use in pipes, window frames, and construction materials and is often used in disposable food containers and for packaging purposes (Gabriel et al., 2025; Nihei et al., 2024).

Various microscopic methods are used to extract, identify, and characterise MP in the environmental samples (Vasudeva et al., 2025). Stereomicroscopes, fluorescent

microscopes, Scanning Electron Microscopes (SEM), and Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) are used to visualise morphological characteristics of extracted microplastics from collected samples. For polymer identification, additional chemical analysis such as Fourier-Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy, Raman Microscopy, and Attenuated Total Reflectance (ATR) are required (Silva et al., 2018). FTIR is effective for the large-sized particles ($500 \mu\text{m} <$), whereas Raman Microscopy can analyse comparatively smaller particles ($< 1 \mu\text{m}$) (Fu et al., 2020; Shim et al., 2017). Thermal analysis techniques such as Pyrolysis Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (Py-GC-MS) and Thermal Desorption Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (TED-GC-MS) are used to detect polymer types by analysing their thermal degradation patterns (Boakye et al., 2025). However, a study conducted by Kppler et al. (2018) found no significant difference in polymer identification using both μ -ATR-FTIR and Py-GC-MS techniques. The extracted particles of the studies limited to the polymeric analysis are considered as Possible Microplastic (PMP).

Several industries and port facilities are located on the banks of the river or the major estuaries. As a result, waste generated from these activities consequently drains into the sea. Moreover, there is a combination of factors that make noticeable plastic debris in the shoreline, including currents, wave action, wind patterns, river discharge, direct littering, industrial wastewater and urban run-off (Dekiff et al., 2014; Magnusson et al., 2016; Rochman, 2018). The persistence of plastics in the environment is attributed to their long chemical chains. Frias et al. (2016) estimated that approximately 80% of marine litter

originates from land-based sources, with a significant portion (70%) eventually sinking to the ocean floor. Studies by Cole et al., (2021) show that oceanographic modelling indicates a large proportion of floating debris reaching the ocean will accumulate in gyres, which are the centres of vast anti-cyclonic, subtropical ocean currents. Moreover, Lagrangian drifters have also been used in more recent studies, indicating that a high proportion of floating marine debris will finally end up in ocean gyres and the ocean bed.

Studies indicate that exposure to microplastics can result in physical toxicity, causing oxidative stress, cellular damage, and inflammatory responses, as well as immune reactions and DNA damage to the human body (Cox et al., 2019). Additionally, Dick Vethaak & Legler (2021) predict that microplastics may act as vectors for hazardous chemicals and pathogens, potentially exacerbating their toxic effects on the body. Revel et al. (2018) and Yuan et al. (2019) also warn that MPs' persistence and mobility exacerbate ecological risks, particularly as plastics degrade and accumulate in aquatic systems (Hale et al., 2020). As a consequence of their impacts, research on microplastics has gradually increased. In the late 1960s, research on microplastics was a curiosity; through the 1970s and 1980s, when most of the threats to marine systems were identified, baseline data were collected on the distribution, abundance, and impacts of marine litter, and policies were formulated to tackle this emerging problem (Bergmann et al., 2015). Still, there is little knowledge about the absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion of microplastics in both aquatic and terrestrial environments.

In recent years, microplastics (MPs) have been reported worldwide in various environmental

matrices (Andrady, 2011a; Frias et al., 2016; Gao et al., 2022; Mutshekwa et al., 2025; Stolte et al., 2015; Villanova-Solano et al., 2022; Zhu et al., 2021a, Xu & Gao, 2025). Recent research by Banik et al. (2024) reveals alarming MP contamination in Northern Bay of Bengal estuaries, with the Karnaphuli River's surface water (350 ± 69.22 items/m³) and Matamuhuri River's sediments (118.33 ± 26.81 items/kg) showing the highest levels, dominated by transparent polyethylene (PE). Parvin, Nath, et al. (2022a) and Rakib et al. (2021) observed similar fibre-dominated MP distributions in Saint Martin's Island beach sediments, while Haque et al. (2022) and Jamal et al. (2025) reported significant MP concentrations in sewage and fish, respectively. Despite these findings, Sonadia Island's MP dynamics remain understudied.

Therefore, the present study endeavours to investigate (a) the abundance and distribution of MP, (b) the morphological characteristics (colour, shape, and size) of MP, and (c) the contamination scenario of Sonadia Island by performing risk assessment indices. This study will help to address the concentration of marine litter, plan possible mitigation methods to reduce inputs, and evaluate the efficacy of such measures. The findings will also assist the government of Bangladesh and neighbouring nations in monitoring and managing waste discharge into the Bay of Bengal and formulating regulatory policies regarding this devastating issue.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

Sonadia Island is a small island of Bangladesh, which is approximately 9 square kilometres

(3.5 square miles) off the coast of Cox's Bazar, Chattogram Division. Sonadia Island is located 15 kilometres northwest of Cox's Bazar District, near Kutubjom Union in Maheshkhali Upazila. The Bakkali and Matamohori rivers, along with many other major rivers, flow into the Bay of Bengal's Maheshkhali Channel. The island is bordered by the Bay of Bengal on the west and south, and so it is impacted by the monsoon wind, high humidity, and mild temperature (Al Nahian et al., 2023). The island has undergone significant geomorphological changes, including coastal erosion and accretion. According to the Tide-Forecast (2025) report, tidal range exceeds 3.35 meters during spring tides, which shape the island's dynamic environment. Sedimentation has driven an impressive accretion rate of 0.29 km² per year, fueled by the Ganges-Brahmaputra-Meghna river system and longshore current between 2001 and 2021. On the contrary, erosion has occurred at a modest rate of 0.3 km² per year, affecting the northwestern and southern edges of the island (Hossain et al., 2023). The sedimentation and hydrodynamic forces resulted in a net gain of 14.09 km² since 1972. Additionally, about 8 km² of mangrove expansion has played a vital role in stabilising newly accreted areas (Hossain et al., 2023). The shore of the island is largely sandy and swamped with brackish water. The study area includes agricultural land, fishing activities, and low human settlements. The samples were collected during low tide (Table 1). Figure 1 illustrates the geographical position of sampling points in the study area.

Table 1: Sampling Points in the Study Area

Sample Code	Sampling Time	Sampling Point	Latitude	Longitude
SON-SND-01	7.45 am-8.04 am	East Beach	21.473517	91.895750
SON-SND-02	8.45 am -9.02 am	Middle Beach	21.480783	91.887683
SON-SND-03	9.28 am-9.45 am	Middle Beach	21.487333	91.875900
SON-SND-04	10.10 am-10.26 am	West Beach	21.499050	91.865517
SON-SND-05	11.15 am-11.40 am	West Beach	21.508950	91.855483

Figure 1: Geographical Location of the Sampling Site. The map is created using ArcGIS Pro 10.8

2.2 Sample Collection

A comprehensive field survey was carried out during March 2024 to collect sand samples from Sonadia Island. During the field survey, sand samples were collected from East Beach, Middle Beach, and West Beach. The sample collection area was marked by defining a transect of 100 m length parallel to the shoreline and above the high tide line corresponding to the daily tide cycle, followed by the method explained in (Burgess et al.,

2021). Along each 100 m transect, five 50×50 cm quadrats were placed at 20m intervals. Each quadrant was divided into 4 sections; the section of the quadrant from which the sample was collected was randomly designated before sampling to avoid bias. The first centimetre of sand was collected using a metal spoon in the chosen section. Sediment samples were collected from five stations along the Coast of Sonadia Island, and five replicas from each station were sampled. Stones and other materials larger than 10 mm in size were

discarded. The identification of the samples was carried out using a unique and unambiguous code (Sampling Site-Matrix-Station-Replica) using the improvised method of (Burgess et al., 2021)

2.3 Sample Processing

Samples were oven-dried at $\leq 50^{\circ}\text{C}$ until a constant weight was achieved. To avoid contamination of the samples by particles present in the laboratory environment, the sample was wrapped with aluminium foil during drying. Some perforations of the paper were made to allow water to exit through evaporation. Once samples had dried and reached a constant weight, the dry weight of each sample was recorded in the corresponding datasheet, following Masura et al. (2015). Separately, each sample was placed in the automatic sieve shaker (Haver & Boekere 59302 OELDE, made in Germany) and cascade sifting was done using 300 μm , 1 mm, and 5 mm sieves for a minimum of 15 minutes. The fractions retained in the sieves of 300 μm (300 $\mu\text{m} \leq$ fraction < 1 mm) and 1 mm (1 mm \leq fraction < 5 mm) were recovered and transferred to the respective labelled beakers. Any material retained on the 5 mm sieves was discarded.

Density separation was performed separately for each of the size fractions obtained from cascade sieving, following the modified laboratory procedures of Masura et al., (2015), Al Nahian et al., (2023) A saturated and filtered (50 μm) NaCl solution ($>1.2 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$) was added to a large glass beaker (<1000 ml), ensuring that the solution was about five times the volume of the sample. The beaker was covered with aluminium foil and stirred gently for 20-30 minutes on a magnetic stirring plate.

After agitation, the samples were allowed to stand overnight. The supernatant was collected and filtered through a 90 μm metal filter (47 mm diameter) using a vacuum filtration system. Once the entire sample had been filtered, the walls of the flask or filtration funnel were rinsed using pre-filtered deionised water to collect any remaining particles and eliminate possible traces of salt precipitates that might have formed during the process.

To facilitate the removal of organic compounds, the samples were digested with 5 mL of 30-35% hydrogen peroxide when organic matter was detected in the sample. The volume of H_2O_2 , ranging from 5 to 10 mL, was determined based on the concentration of organic matter.

2.4 Identification of Microplastics

MPs isolated from the sand sample were identified, counted, and photographed using a ZEISS Stemi 305 Stereomicroscope with 40 \times magnification and ZEISS ZEN core v3.2 software. MP particles are evaluated according to their size and form. MP shapes include fibres, pieces, pellets, films, and foam. MPs are also classed by colour, with options including white, black, blue, green, purple, red, and translucent. This work has limitations in terms of polymer characterisation. For a conclusive polymeric identification, either FTIR or Raman spectroscopy is required (Käppler et al., 2018).

2.5 Risk Assessment Indices

To examine the microplastic pollution load across Sonadia Island, risk assessment indices such as Contamination Factor (CF) and Pollution Load Index (PLI) were utilised, as shown in Table 2. The risk assessment model was followed by the formula described in Al Nahian et al., (2023a;) and Tomlinson et al., (1980).

1. Contamination factor

$$CF = \frac{C_i}{C_o}$$

2. Pollution load index

$$PLI = \sqrt[n]{CF_1 \times CF_2 \times CF_3 \times \dots \times CF_n}$$

where i signifies the station, n is the number of stations, C_i represents microplastic abundance at the i^{th} station, and C_o symbolises the minimum microplastic abundance observed during this study, i.e., baseline microplastic concentration in Sonadia Island (as no microplastic study was performed previously). Moreover, the Pollution Load Index (PLI) is the geometric mean of the contamination factor of selected stations.

Table 2: Category engaged in the MPs' risk assessment

Risk Assessment	Values	Risk Categories	References
Contamination Factor (CF)	<1	Low contamination	(Al Nahian et al., 2023; Tomlinson et al., 1980)
	1-3	Moderate contamination	
	3-6	Considerable Contamination	
	≥ 6	Very High Contamination	
Pollution Load Index (PLI)	> 1	Polluted	(Rakib et al., 2022)

2.6 Data Analysis

To quantify the level of pollution on Sonadia Island, mean values for MP pollution data were paired with their standard deviation. The graphical appearance was enhanced with MS Excel. The study area map and MP abundance analysis corresponding to the sampling locations were created using ArcGIS Pro 10.8. MP concentration was analysed based on size, shape, and colour distribution.

2.7 Contamination Control

To restrict MP contamination, all liquids were filtered through a 90 μm metal filter mesh before use. Aside from that, glass materials and beakers were cleaned with deionised

water. To prevent external contamination while not being analysed, each sediment sample was covered with aluminium foil. To avoid external contamination, preliminary control procedures were implemented throughout sample collection, transportation, and processing.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1 Occurrence of Microplastics

Possible Microplastics (PMP) were identified in every sampling location on Sonadia Island, with an average of 17.68 ± 7.88 Particles kg^{-1} in dry sand samples. In this experiment, the greatest mean value of PMPs was (40 ± 19.02 Particles kg^{-1}) in sampling site S2, followed by

S1 (17.8 ± 5.35 Particles kg^{-1}), S3 (12.53 ± 3.91 Particles kg^{-1}), S4 (9.39 ± 5.6 Particles kg^{-1}), and finally, in the lowest interrupted zone, S5 (8.66 ± 5.46 Particles kg^{-1}). The largest abundances in S2 and S1 suggested that the MP load in beach sand could be due to fishing

fishing activities (Bessa et al., 2018; Rahman et al., 2020; Tajwar et al., 2022; Yuan et al., 2019). The present study reveals a significant concentration of possible microplastics (PMP) at sampling sites S2 and S1. These sites are subject to exposure from salt production

Figure 2: Concentration of PMP a. Box Plot Analysis of abundance (particles/kg) b. Percentage in each station

activities (Figure 2).

The results found in this study have been compared with other sediment studies (Table 3). The mean abundance of this study site was found to be higher than that in Cox's Bazar (Rahman et al., 2020), Portugal (Frias et al., 2016). This investigation also demonstrated that the concentration was substantially lower than that in Kuakata (Banik et al., 2022), Bohai Sea China (Zhu et al., 2021), Island in India (Tiwari et al., 2019), Southern United States (Yu et al., 2017), and Indonesia (Syakti et al., 2018).

The study by Magnusson et al. (2016) claimed that laundry effluent and industrial discharge can cause MP (microfibre) load in beach sediment. Previous studies revealed that MP contamination was positively correlated with tourism activities, industrial discharge, and

farms and dry fish processing activities, suggesting a potential correlation between PMP concentration and these activities. In contrast, three other sampling sites (S3, S4, S5), located in remote areas, exhibited comparatively lower concentrations of microplastics, with percentages of 14%, 11%, and 10%, respectively, which are lower than those observed at sites S1 (20%) and S2 (45%).

3.2 Size Distribution of the PMP

The primary focus of this investigation was on microplastics (MPs) with a range of 0.3 to 5 mm. The observed PMPs, a total of 227 particles, were categorised into two groups: those with a size range of 1 to 5 mm, comprising 48%, and those ranging from 0.3

to 1 mm, comprising 52% (Figure 5). While our findings align with those of some authors (Bappy et al., 2025; Jamal et al., 2025; Mia et al., 2024; Mubin et al., 2024). On the other hand, a study by Al Nahian et al. (2023a) and Hossain et al. (2021) reported that plastic particles of 1 to 5mm size were predominant in their studies conducted in the Moheshkhali channel and Cox's Bazar, respectively.

Notably, particles ranging from 0.3 to 1 mm were more prevalent at sites S1, S2, and S5,

with site S2 exhibiting a slightly higher concentration of larger particles. The most common type of smaller particle was fibre. Fragments were discovered to be larger. Microplastic size distribution results from diverse sources, degradation processes, and transport mechanisms. The initial size of microplastics is determined by their origin, whether from the breakdown of larger plastics or direct release as microbeads (Andrady, 2011a).

Figure 3: Relative abundance of PMP among different sites. The map is created using ArcGIS 10.8

Figure 4: Microscopic images of some extracted PMP, Fibre (a,b,c,h), Film (g), Fragment (d,e,f), Foam (i) Subsequent weathering and fragmentation reduce particle sizes, creating a wide range. The shapes and sizes of MP indicate that they may undergo degradation and weathering processes (Figure 4). Moreover, a Study by Enders et al., (2015) reported that small microplastic is widely dispersed throughout the ocean surface layer and have lower residence times compared to larger plastic debris in this compartment.

Table 3: Concentration of MP in several studies

Location	Sample Type	Mean Abundance	Dominant Type	Reference
Sonadia Island, Bangladesh	Sand	17.68 ± 7.88 Particles/kg	Fibre 74%	Present Study
Kuakata, Bangladesh	Beach Sediment	232 ± 52 items/kg	Fibre 55%	(Banik et al., 2022)
Cox’s Bazar, Bangladesh	Beach Sediment	8.1 ± 2.9 particles/kg	Fragments (64%)	(Rahman et al., 2020)
Bohai Sea, China	Sediment	280.0 to 773.4 items/kg	Fibre 77.1%	(Zhu et al., 2021)
Mediterranean Sea	Sediment	113.2 ± 88.9 Particles/kg	Fibre 82.9%	(Filgueiras et al., 2019)
Portugal	Sediment	17.9 items/kg	Fibre 80.64%	(Frias et al., 2016)
Southeastern United States	Sediment	60-100 pieces/kg	Fibres 68%	(Yu et al., 2017)
El Salvador Coast Central America	Sand	48 to 300 items/m ²	Fibre 85.9%	(Quintanilla et al., 2025)

Subsequent weathering and fragmentation reduce particle sizes, creating a wide range. The shapes and sizes of MP indicate that they may undergo degradation and weathering processes (Figure 4). Moreover, a Study by Enders et al., (2015) reported that small microplastic is widely dispersed throughout the ocean surface layer and have lower residence times compared to larger plastic debris in this compartment.

Figure 5: Size Distribution of PMP

Figure 6: Shape Distribution of PMP among Stations

3.3 Characteristics of PMP

Fibres were recorded to be the most frequent shape type, similar to the result of (Banik et al., 2022, Fibre 55%), (Zhu et al., 2021b, Fibre, 77.1%) (Filgueiras et al., 2019, Fibre 82.9%). The distribution of microplastics based on MP shape was as follows: fibre (74%), fragment (18%), film (7%), and foam (1%) (Figure 6). Other studies found that fibre was the most common MP type in industrial waste, sludge, and zooplankton (Haque et al., 2022; Taha et al., 2021). Again, fibre was discovered in all locations and remained more concentrated than other forms in this study. The second abundant form of the extracted particles was

fragments, which were found in all stations and had a slightly higher concentration in S2. Although fragments were shown to be the most predominant form in several investigations (Al Nahian et al., 2022; Campanale et al., 2020; Rahman et al., 2020). Foam was the least common type, appearing in three of the 25 stations (including Replica). Films have been reported as the prevalent form in various studies performed by Al Nahian et al., (2023a) and Rakib et al., (2022) which is not similar to the current study.

Since this study region is close to a salt pan and a dry fish processing facility, the materials

utilised in this activity (rope, net) could contribute significantly as a main source. Microplastic concentrations are most likely to come from city wastes, industrial production sites, fishing, and tourism-associated activities, according to Stolte et al., (2015). MP isolated from sediment samples had a variety

of hues. The hues observed include white, blue, red, green, pink, black, and transparent (Figure 7). The distribution was as follows: Transparent (72%), followed by red (10%), blue (5%), black (5%), white (4%), green (2%), and pink (2%).

Figure 7: Colour Distribution of PMP

3.4 Sources of Microplastics

The microplastic (MP) concentration found in Sonadia Island's beach sand is likely affected by the combined influence of local and regional sources and transport mechanisms. Potential sources of MP in the coastal sediment and waterbodies of the Northern Bay of Bengal include the fragmentation and degradation of fishing gears (e.g., plastic lines, ropes, nets) and plastic bags (Jamal et al., 2025). Similarly, a study conducted by Bappy et al. (2025) on surface waters of two public beaches (Potenga & Parki) along the Northern Bay of Bengal found similar sources of MP, which also suggests industrial discharges, urban runoff, and tourism-associated practices as primary pathways. These findings

align with a conceptual model highlighting riverine inputs as significant vectors for MP transport from inland areas to coastal zones. Local activities, such as fishing and shipping, may further exacerbate MP presence on these beaches.

However, studies in other regions of Bangladesh suggest varying contributions from different sources. For example, Rahman et al. (2020) found that tourism-related activities contributed more to elevated MP levels in Cox's Bazar beach sediments than tidal activities, drift currents, wind action, or land-based anthropogenic sources like commercial fishing and industrial discharges. While the exact sources of plastic debris in this study could not be verified, urban runoff in

winter and marine sources during summer were suggested based on seasonal current alterations. The relatively high concentration of fibres found in Sonadia Island's beach sand suggests a contribution from fishing-related activities and industrial discharge, which needs to be verified.

3.5 Risk Assessment

A risk assessment was conducted for each sampling station in this study region. The contamination factor (CF) indicated moderate to considerable contamination. According to the listed range of contamination factors, sampling sites S1, S3, S4, and S5 are

moderately contaminated, and S2 is considerably contaminated, as seen in this image. By calculating the 5th root of the product of the five contamination factor values, the Pollution Load Index (PLI) was found to be 1.716 (Table 4), which is larger than one. These values imply that the examined area is contaminated. The results of this investigation are aligned with the contamination status of the sediment in five major estuaries and islands (Banik et al., 2024; Mubin et al., 2024). Moreover, the results demonstrate lower pollution conditions than those of the Karnaphuli River Estuary sediments (Rakib et al., 2022).

Table 4: Risk Assessment (CF, PLI)

Station	Abundance (Particles/ kg)	Contamination Factor (CF)	Mean CF	Pollution Load Index (PLI)
S1	17.818	2.057	2.041	1.716
S2	40.008	4.618		
S3	12.535	1.447		
S4	9.397	1.085		
S5	8.663	1		

4. Limitation

This study provides valuable insights and understanding into the microplastic contamination scenario in Sonadia Island. The focus of the study was on beach sand samples from five high tide line stations, which limits the spatial distribution of MP across the beach face of the study area. The dependency on merely stereomicroscopic analysis for the visual identification of microplastics can result in subjectivity and potential inaccuracy, especially for small-sized MP. The lack of polymer identification acts as a barrier to source apportionment and the assessment of polymer-specific ecological impact. Moreover,

the counting of "Possible Microplastic" (PMPs), though acknowledging identification uncertainties, may increase MP concentration by including non-plastic particles. This study is limited to temporal distribution, as the sampling process was a single event. Lack of seasonal data may hinder the understanding of the changes in concentration. The absence of direct source allocation, relying solely on morphological interference, diminishes source identification. Finally, the study's restriction on ecological assessment leaves the broader environmental consequences unexplored. Addressing these limitations through expanded spatial and temporal sampling, polymer analysis, source tracking,

and ecological assessment is critical for a comprehensive understanding of MP pollution and formulating effective mitigation strategies.

5. Conclusion

The study provides important baseline data on microplastic pollution in the beach sands of Sonadia Island, revealing a mean concentration of 17.68 ± 7.88 particles/kg. The morphological distribution exhibits that fibres are the dominant type of microplastic (74%), followed by fragments (18%), films (7%), and foam (1%). The majority (52%) of particles are between 0.3 and 1 mm in size. Though the concentration recorded is lower than the global average, the contamination factor (CF) and Pollution Load Index (PLI) indicate moderate to considerable pollution levels across the study area. The high abundance of fibres suggests that fishing activities and industrial discharge are likely primary sources. However, further investigation on pollution pathways is required to understand the pollution source of this island ecosystem.

The findings underscore the urgent need for environmental management strategies to reduce emerging microplastic contamination in Sonadia Island. Key involvement should focus on reducing plastic consumption, establishing waste management infrastructure, enhancing recycling efforts, and growing public awareness. A multi-stakeholder approach involving the government, private agencies, and local communities will be effective for developing and enforcing effective measures.

Future research direction should prioritise advanced polymer identification, sources and

pathways, and environmental impacts. Moreover, the role of microplastics as a vector for escalating other hazards, such as heavy metals, should be explored to understand their impact on marine and coastal ecosystems. These investigations will provide critical data to inform conservation strategies and help to protect the coastal ecosystem. The current study establishes a foundation for ongoing monitoring efforts to mitigate plastic pollution in the coastal environment and to achieve Sustainable Development Goal (SDG).

Source of Fund

This research was funded by IAEA-TC Project-RAS 7038 (Monitoring the Marine Environment for Enhanced Understanding of the Abundance and Impact of Marine Plastic Pollution)

Author Contribution

“Conceptualization, Dr. Shahadat Hossain, Professor Dr. Mohammad Muslem Uddin; methodology, Afrin Sultana Sadia, Nighat Sultana Resma; software, Nighat Sultana Resma, Afrin Sultana Sadia; validation, Afrin Sultana Sadia, Nighat Sultana Resma, Professor Dr. Mohammad Muslem Uddin, Dr. Shahadat Hossain; formal analysis and investigation, Afrin Sultana Sadia, Nighat Sultana Resma; resources, Dr. Shahadat Hossain; data curation Afrin Sultana Sadia, Nighat Sultana Resma; writing—original draft preparation Afrin Sultana Sadia; writing—review and editing Afrin Sultana Sadia, Nighat Sultana Resma, Professor Dr. Mohammad Muslem Uddin, Dr. Shahadat Hossain; supervision Professor Dr. Mohammad Muslem Uddin, Dr. Shahadat Hossain. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge the Atomic Energy Centre, Chattogram (AECC), for laboratory and technical support. The Department of Oceanography, University of Chittagong, is also acknowledged for institutional facilities. All other contributors are sincerely appreciated.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest among them.

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